

The Effect of Cropping Systems on component crop productivity and Land Resource Use Efficiency

Abstract

Adoption of intercropping has the potential to make efficient use of scarce land resource in densely populated AEZs of western Kenya and provide both livestock feed and human food while ensuring climate resilience. Most studies have focused on one intercrop while in this study, we tested Maize-*Desmodium* intercrop with vegetables on system productivity and land equivalent ratio (LER). Field experiment was conducted during short rains of 2023 and long rains of 2024 in Maseno to determine the effect of integrating kales and African nightshade into Maize-*Desmodium spp* intercrop on productivity of component crops and LER. Treatments consisted of sole Maize, *Desmodium*, Kales and Nightshade and their intercropping components of Maize-*Desmodium*, Maize-*Desmodium*-kales, Maize-*Desmodium*-Nightshade, Kales-*Desmodium* and Nightshade-*Desmodium*, arranged in RCBD with three replications. Data was collected on plant yields and used to determine land equivalent ratio (LER) and analysed using R software and significant means separated using $LSD_{0.05}$. Maize yields in all cropping systems were not statistically significant in both seasons although Maize-*Desmodium*-kales had a slightly higher yields than other cropping systems on both season. Nightshade and Kales had no significant effect on dry matter biomass yield. Sole *Desmodium* (2.84t/ha) and Kale-*Desmodium* (2.34t/ha) had a significantly higher dry matter yield during the short rains but during the long rains, sole *Desmodium* (2.69t/ha) had a significantly higher dry matter. The LER for Maize-*Desmodium*-nightshade (2.8 and 1.96) and Maize-*Desmodium*-kales (2.45 and 1.88) was significantly higher indicating positive complimentary interaction between the crops. Intercropping *Desmodium* with maize and kales or nightshade increases maize yields. Additionally, intercropping of *Desmodium* with maize, kales or nightshade significantly improves the land use efficiency.

Keywords

Intercropping, Productivity, LER, climate resilience

Introduction

The availability of land for agriculture has become limited due to growing population and utilization of non-agricultural activities (Jiang *et al.*, 2013). For instance, intercropping allows for a more efficient use of land resources where different crops are grown on the same space (Stomph *et al.*, 2020). This ensures that, the available resources are used more effectively, minimizing waste and improving overall productivity (Paudel, 2016). According to Altieri *et al.*, (2015), intercropping unlike monoculture, enhance yield stability of the component crops. Different crops have different root structures and growth habits, which can help to prevent soil erosion and improve soil health (Fahad *et al.*, 2022). Furthermore, the continuous cover provided by multiple crops can reduce water evaporation, helping to conserve water (Wang *et al.*, 2021). Maize-*Desmodium spp* cropping system has been instrumental in increasing

maize yield in addition to controlling *Striga hermonthica* and pests. *Desmodium spp*, a type of leguminous fodder, plays a crucial role in this system. It has the unique ability to fix atmospheric nitrogen, thereby enriching the soil with this essential nutrient. In addition, it contributes to increasing the soil organic matter, significantly improving carbon sequestration and the uptake of phosphorus through synergistic interaction of N (Bamboriya *et al.*, 2022; Ndiritu, 2022). Hence offers an effective alternative to the use of inorganic fertilizers, which can be expensive. By covering the ground, *Desmodium spp* helps in conservation of soil moisture, reduces soil erosion and suppresses the growth of Striga weeds (Osieyo, 2022). Intercropping maize with various vegetables, like tomato, onions, kale, nightshade, cowpea and spinach, can also be productive. These combinations allow for a more efficient use of space and resources, while also providing a diverse diet for local communities (Henze *et al.*, 2020). However, there is a gap in research regarding the dynamics of soil moisture and nutrients, and how these dynamics affect crop productivity due to interspecific competition within this new system.

Materials and methods

Experimental site description

The experiment was carried out in Maseno university farm, Kisumu County which lies at Latitude: N00.00304 and Longitude: E034.59989 and is approximately 1526 masl. Maseno receives a mean rainfall of 1500-1700mm annually with bimodal rain distribution of short rains(August-December) and long rains(March-July). The minimum mean temperature ranges between 10-18⁰C and the maximum mean temperature ranges between 25-30⁰C.The main soil types are well drained, deep reddish to brown clay-loamy Ferralsol with slightly acidic (Sikuku., 2010).

Experimental design and layout

The experiment comprised 9 treatments replicated 3 times totalling to 27 experimental units. All treatments were arranged in Randomized Complete Block Design(RCBD). Each experimental unit was measuring 4.5x4.5m (20.25m²).

Treatments

Treatments consisted of Maize+*Desmodium* , African nightshhade+*Desmodium*, Kales+*Desmodium*, Maize+Kales+*Desmodium*, Maize+African Nightshade+*Desmodium*, Sole kales, Sole maize, Sole African Nightshade, Sole *Desmodium*. Intercropping of maize and vegetables was superimposed on already established *Desmodium*, where each row of maize and vegetables alternates with *Desmodium*.

Weather data

The daily rainfall and hourly ambient temperature and humidity within the cropping system of the nine treatments was measured using the rainfall and temperature and relative humidity data loggers stationed at the farm.

Crop establishment and management

The experiment was conducted for two seasons of short rains of 2023 and long rains of 2024. Land was prepared during the dry season to control weeds and improve soil structure with a nursery bed prepared for vegetables seedlings three weeks before transplanting. Due to acidic soil on the site, lime was applied at a recommended rate at 2t/ha through broadcasting and hand harrowed properly with a fork hoe. *Desmodium spp* was trimmed before planting Maize and vegetables at a spacing of 75cm between rows and 30cm within rows. Planting holes were created using a hand hoe. Since phosphorus was adequate from our soil analysis only CAN fertilizer (40kg N/Ha) was applied in two stages at planting and at 5th leaf stage of maize to ensure adequate nitrogen supply. Stand count on maize and vegetables was taken two weeks after planting. Weeding was done at two and six weeks after crops establishment. Maize was sprayed with Pyrethrin pesticide to control fall army worm infestation while vegetables was sprayed with Dudutrin to control leaf miners, aphids and diamond black moth.

Data collection

Maize yield and biomass determination

Plant yields

Plant yield on maize crop was determined at physiological maturity. Two middle rows was harvested in each maize associated treatment and the ear number, field ear weight and moisture content determined. Maize grain yield per hectare was calculated using the following formulae;

$$\text{Grain yield (t/ha)} = \left[\frac{\text{FW (kg/plot)} \times 10 \times (100 - \text{MC}) \times 0.8}{(100 - \text{adjusted MC}) \times \text{Plot Area}} \right]$$

Whereby;

FW= Field ear weight in kg

MC= Field moisture content

Adjusted MC= moisture content adjusted to 13%

Shelling coefficient=0.8

Harvested area= 6.75m²

The above ground biomass was computed by sampling 4 plants obtained from 6.75m² harvesting area. After weighing the 4 plants, shoots, leaves and cobs was chopped into small pieces and placed in khaki bags. These were taken to the laboratory and oven dried at 70⁰C for 24hrs before taking dry weight.

Vegetable Dry Matter Determination

Two middle rows of each vegetable was harvested 3 times during each season at an interval of 2 weeks starting at 3 weeks after planting. After taking fresh weight, a sample was taken for dry matter determination by oven drying at 70⁰C for 24hrs. Dry weight was taken which was used to calculate dry matter weight per unit area. At the end of each season, two middle rows of *Desmodium spp* in each plot was harvested, fresh weigh and sun dried for 4 days for total dry matter biomass determination.

Land Equivalent Ratio

Data collected on maize, vegetables and *Desmodium* yields was used to determine the yield advantage of intercropping kales and African Nightshade into the maize-*Desmodium* cropping system over the sole cropping system described by (Mead & Willey, 1980).

$$LER = La + Lb + Lc = \frac{Ya}{Sa} + \frac{Yb}{Sb} + \frac{Yc}{Sc}$$

Where L_a , L_b , and L_c are the LERs for the individual crops (maize, *Desmodium spp*, kales or african nightshade). Y_a , Y_b , and Y_c are the yields of individual crops in intercropping, while S_a , S_b , and S_c are the yields of the sole crops.

Data analysis

The data collected were subjected to analysis of variance (ANOVA) and significant means separated using least significance difference ($LSD_{0.05}$) to determine significance differences between the treatments for LER, maize grain yield and dry matter yields of maize, vegetables and *Desmodium*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSION

Weather

Short raining season recorded a total of 941.8mm rainfall between September and December 2023 and the long rains recorded a total of 749.2mm rainfall between March to August 2024. The average mean monthly temperature during the short rains were 25.6°C and 23.1°C during the long rains season. The month of May received the highest amount of rainfall while the month of December received the lowest amount of rainfall during the short rain season (Fig. 1). During the long rains, May and July receive the highest and lowest amount of rainfall respectively. The monthly average temperature during the short rains were lowest in November (20.3°C) and highest in December (25.3°C) while in long rains, monthly average temperature was recorded lowest in March (21.5°C) and highest in July(24.6°C).

Fig 1; Maseno rainfall and temperature during cropping season.

Effect of cropping system on plant yields.

The effect of cropping system had no significant effect on maize yields in all season. However, Maize-*Desmodium spp*- kales had a slightly higher yields (1.68t/ha) during the SR and (1.63t/ha) during the LR (Table 1).

Table 1; Effect of cropping system on maize grain yield.

CROP	CROPPING SYSTEM	Yields(t/ha)	
		SR2023	LR2024
MAIZE	<i>Maize-Desmodium- kales</i>	1.68a	1.63a
	<i>Maize-Desmodium</i>	1.53a	1.36a
	<i>Maize-Desmodium-</i>	1.55a	1.31a
	<i>nightshade</i>		
	<i>Sole maize</i>	1.53a	1.35a
	LSD	NS	NS
	CV	17.60	24.46
MEAN	1.57	1.41	

Key

Means of the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

SR2023 = Short rains of 2023 cropping season

LR2024 = Long rains of 2024 cropping season

Effects of cropping system on kales, nightshade, desmodium dry matter yield

The dry matter weight on Nightshade and Kales in the cropping system had no significant effect (Table 2 and Table 3). *Desmodium spp*, Sole *Desmodium spp* (2.84t/ha) and Kale-*Desmodium spp* (2.34t/ha) had a significant dry matter yield during the SR but during the LR sole *Desmodium spp* (2.69t/ha) had a significant dry matter compared with the other cropping systems (Table 4). Cropping system had no significant effect on yields of maize crop which might be attributed to the compatibility of the plant combination of the cropping system in terms of a balance in uptake of nutrients, water and light, it could have also been contributed by the favourable microclimatic condition created within the cropping system. Singh *et al.*, (2012) demonstrated that the microclimate under short and tall crops reduce solar radiation, lowers red:far-red ratio light and lowers evapotranspiration thus enhancing intercrop yields. Sole *Desmodium spp* and *Desmodium spp* intercropped with kale recorded significantly higher dry matter yield compared with *Desmodium spp* from other cropping system. Kifuko *et al.*, (2012) found that *Desmodium spp* when intercropped with maize has little effect on maize yield, but affects

Desmodium biomass production. This implies that sole *Desmodium spp* which is shorter requires maximum sunlight to perform well. The significantly higher dry matter weight of *Demodium spp* in Kale-*Desmodium spp* intercrop could be attributed to resource balance and compatibility of the cropping system while *Desmodium spp* in other intercrops performed poorly which could be due to light and space stress when intercropped.

Table 2; Effects of cropping system on kales dry matter yield

CROPPING SYSTEM	Dry weight (t/ha)	
	SR2023	LR2024
<i>Maize-kales-desmodium</i>	0.26a	0.83a
<i>Kales-desmodium</i>	0.23a	0.82a
<i>Sole kales</i>	0.21a	0.82a
LSD	NS	NS
CV	24.65	5.78
MEAN	0.23	0.82

Key

Means of the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

SR2023 = Short rains of 2023 cropping season

LR2024 = Long rains of 2024 cropping season

Table 3; Effects of cropping system on Nightshade dry matter (t/ha)

CROPPING SYSTEM	Dry weight (t/ha)	
	SR2023	LR2024
<i>Maize-desmodium-nightshade</i>	2.38a	0.56a
<i>Nightshade-desmodium</i>	1.81a	0.48a
<i>Sole nightshade</i>	1.68a	0.61a
LSD	NS	NS
CV	21.68	0.55
MEAN	1.96	0.37

Key

Means of the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

SR2023 = Short rains of 2023 cropping season

LR2024 = Long rains of 2024 cropping season

Table 4; Effects of cropping system on Desmodium dry matter (t/ha)

CROPPING SYSTEM	Dry weight(t/ha)	
	SR2023	LR2024
<i>Maize-desmodium-kales</i>	1.64c	1.55b
<i>Kales-desmodium</i>	2.34ab	1.17b
<i>Maize-desmodium</i>	2.19bc	1.76b
<i>Maize-desmodium-nightshade</i>	2.02bc	1.92b
<i>Nightshade-desmodium</i>	1.73bc	1.92b
<i>Sole desmodium</i>	2.84a	2.69a
LSD	0.639	1.95
CV	16.52	29.9
MEAN	2.126	3.67

Key

Means of the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

SR2023 = Short rains of 2023 cropping season

LR2024 = Long rains of 2024 cropping season

Effect of cropping system on Land Equivalent Ratio

The total LER of all the five intercropping system were greater than 1 indicating that intercropping systems had a yield advantage over the sole crops (Table 5). Takim, (2012) also found similar results that intercropping were higher in intercrops, indicating an optimum exploitation of resources. *Maize-Desmodium-nightshade* (2.8t/ha and 1.96t/ha) had significantly higher LER than *Nightshade-desmodium*, *kale desmodium* and *maize-desmodium* in both seasons respectively. Although LER for *Maize-Desmodium-Nightshade* and *Maize-Desmodium-Kale* were not significantly different, the study shows that three intercrops are better than two intercrops. This could be attributed to the favourable microclimatic condition created between the three intercrops due to the positive interaction among them.

Table 5; Effect of cropping system on Land Equivalent Ratio.

LER		
CROPPING SYSTEM	SR2023	LR2024
<i>Maize-Desmodium-nightshade</i>	2.80a	1.96a
<i>Maize-Desmodium- kales</i>	2.45ab	1.88ab
<i>Nightshade-Desmodium</i>	1.46b	1.21c
<i>Kales-Desmodium</i>	1.46b	1.48bc
<i>Maize-Desmodium</i>	1.42b	1.39c
Mean	1.918	1.58
CV%	29.64	15.76
LSD	1.07	0.47

Key

Means of the same letter are not significantly different from each other.

SR2023 = Short rains of 2023 cropping season

LR2024 = Long rains of 2024 cropping season

Conclusion

Intercropping *Desmodium* with maize and kales or nightshade significantly increases the growth and yields of component crops except *Desmodium*. Additionally, intercropping of *Desmodium* with maize, kales or nightshade significantly improves the land use efficiency compared to mono-cropping. The variation observed in the two season points out the important role that environmental factors contributes to crop performance

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References

- Altieri, M. A., Nicholls, C. I., Henao, A., & Lana, M. A. (2015). Agroecology and the design of climate change-resilient farming systems. *Agronomy for Sustainable Development*, 35(3), 869–890. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13593-015-0285-2>
- Bamboriya, S. D., Bana, R. S., Kuri, B. R., Kumar, V., Bamboriya, S. D., & Meena, R. P. (2022). Achieving higher production from low inputs using synergistic crop interactions under maize-based polyculture systems. *Environmental Sustainability*, 5(2), 145–159. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s42398-022-00228-7>
- Chen, G., Liu, M., Zhao, X., Bawa, G., Liang, B., Feng, L., Pu, T., Yong, T., Liu, W., & Liu, J. (2024). Improved photosynthetic performance under unilateral weak light conditions in a wide–narrow-

- row intercropping system is associated with altered sugar transport. *Journal of Experimental Botany*, 75(1), 258–273.
- Fahad, S., Chavan, S. B., Chichaghare, A. R., Uthappa, A. R., Kumar, M., Kakade, V., Pradhan, A., Jinger, D., Rawale, G., Yadav, D. K., Kumar, V., Farooq, T. H., Ali, B., Sawant, A. V., Saud, S., Chen, S., & Poczai, P. (2022). Agroforestry Systems for Soil Health Improvement and Maintenance. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14(22), 1–25. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142214877>
- Henze, J., Abukutsa-Onyango, M., & Opiyo, A. (2020). *Production and Marketing of African Indigenous Leafy Vegetables*. Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin.
- Jiang, L., Deng, X., & Seto, K. C. (2013). The impact of urban expansion on agricultural land use intensity in China. *Land Use Policy*, 35, 33–39. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2013.04.011>
- Mead, R., & Willey, R. W. (1980). The concept of a ‘land equivalent ratio’ and advantages in yields from intercropping. *Experimental Agriculture*, 16(3), 217–228. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0014479700010978>
- Ndiritu, J. M. (2022). *Climate Smart Agricultural Intensification With Desmodium Legume Cover Crops in Coffee Farm at Kabete in Times of Climate Change*. University of Nairobi.
- Osieyo, S. M. (2022). *Comparative effects of maize-soybeans and maize-Desmodium intercropping systems on yield of component crops and rainfall use efficiency in western Kenya*. Maseno University.
- Paudel, M. N. (2016). Multiple cropping for raising productivity and farm income of small farmers. *Journal of Nepal Agricultural Research Council*, 2, 37–45.
- Setiawan, A. N. (2022). Microclimate dynamics in sweet corn intercropping with various legumes. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 985(1), 12013.
- Sikuku P.A., Netondo.G.W., M. D. . and O. J. C. (2010). Effects of Water Deficit on Days To Maturity and Yield of Three NERICA rice varieties. *ARPN Journal of Agricultural and Biological Science*, 5(3), 1–9.
- Singh, A. K., Pravesh Kumar, P. K., Renu Singh, R. S., & Nidhi Rathore, N. R. (2012). *Dynamics of tree-crop interface in relation to their influence on microclimatic changes-a review*.
- Stomph, T. J., Dordas, C., Baranger, A., de Rijk, J., Dong, B., Evers, J., Gu, C., Li, L., Simon, J., Jensen, E. S., Wang, Q., Wang, Y., Wang, Z., Xu, H., Zhang, C., Zhang, L., Zhang, W. P., Bedoussac, L., & van der Werf, W. (2020). Designing intercrops for high yield, yield stability and efficient use of resources: Are there principles? In *Advances in Agronomy* (1st ed., Vol. 160, Issue 1). Elsevier Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/bs.agron.2019.10.002>
- Takim, F. O. (2012). Advantages of maize-cowpea intercropping over sole cropping through competition indices. *Journal of Agriculture and Biodiversity Research*, 1(4), 53–59.
- Wang, J., Zhang, S., Sainju, U. M., Ghimire, R., & Zhao, F. (2021). A meta-analysis on cover crop impact on soil water storage, succeeding crop yield, and water-use efficiency. *Agricultural Water*

Management, 256, 107085.